

**The God Theory: Irrational and Devoid of Proof or Proven
Circumstantially?**

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Abstract

In this qualitative analysis, the researcher explores The God Theory or Intelligent Design. While the atheist community continues to make the assertion that God does not exist through assertions such as there being no direct evidence for God, this analysis of existing research demonstrates the circumstantial case for God. Though some believe circumstantial evidence is not as strong as direct evidence, courts have often found it just as compelling. Hence, the circumstantial evidence from previous studies makes a compelling case for the existence of God. The first major point is that both spontaneous generation and abiogenesis have been proven impossible. This means that the only way life could arise by deduction is from another source of life. Another piece of evidence is that there are aspects to our existence that cannot be quantified yet are real without any doubt. As a result, one can certainly conclude rightly that miraculous events, which have been scientifically proven miraculous are attributable to an intelligent, conscious force, capable of acting deliberately and unable to be quantified or perceived through the senses. While these facts make a circumstantial case for God, the most compelling evidence is the fact that former atheists were converted and expressed the same theme; science and reasoning alone is insufficient to explain human existence as there are intangible elements, which add to the scientific to tell the whole story. When taken as a whole, this compellingly suggests the presence of a divine creator whom the theological community lovingly refers to as God.

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Bernard Goldberg (2021) stated that "circumstantial evidence is evidence." By this, Goldberg was informing the listener that proof which suggests the truth of a statement is just as valid as proof which shows it directly. In fact, history has shown that circumstantial evidence has been found just as compelling by courts as direct evidence. While this holds true, the researcher has observed in the atheistic community the tendency to use the argument that there is no direct evidence of God. Further witnessed has been the rejection of any circumstantial evidence, which establishes His reality by way of inference.

Primarily, one must consider the fact that abiogenesis or life arising from non-living material has been proven impossible from a statistical and scientific standpoint. Moreover, one must consider the supernatural events or miracles occurring in the present day. Also, it is imperative that one understand that life is composed of more than just the tangible and measurable; intangible aspects of the world exist.

Additionally, one must look at a common theme among former atheists who were compelled to convert to Christianity. A major one of which is that knowledge of science in its totality is insufficient to explain the human experience. In making a case for God's existence, there are facts that cannot be denied,

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which when taken as a whole prove by inference the truth of God's existence.

Abiogenesis is defined as "the ability of nonlife to create life (Thompkins, 2018)." Matter exists in only two states, living and nonliving. The fundamental issue that divides the atheist and theological communities is whether or not abiogenesis is possible. In an experiment conducted in 1892, Louis Pasteur used chicken broth, which he boiled in a flask to kill any existing microbial life, and sealed the flask for a year to test whether or not life could spontaneously generate (Dao, 2008). He also set up his contraption so that any airborne bacteria would be caught in a tube, while air could still reach the broth. After a year, no life was found. However, within several days of his opening the flask, microbial life was present. He concluded that microbial life was in the air all along and could not be seen, the dust particles carried them into the broth mixture, and the nutrients in the broth caused the microbes to grow larger by giving them an energy source. Hence, he proved life could not generate spontaneously or be produced from nonlife.

Following Pasteur's groundbreaking work, many in the atheist community argued that abiogenesis was not spontaneous as spontaneous implied it had no cause, yet they believed it to have some sort of a causative agent. Omerbasic (2021) took this

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theory and put it to the test using the concept of human blood plasma, which is made up of 574 amino acids. Using the theoretical probability model, the probability that these 574 amino acids could have evolved by random chance was calculated at 1 in 10 to the 1092nd power. Being that the theoretical probability model by way of Borel's law states that at a probability of 1 in 10 to the 50th power, the event is deemed impossible from a statistical standpoint, the probability of evolving these amino acids randomly with or without cause is greater than 20 times lower than impossible (Omerbasic, 2021). The fact that this refers only to blood plasma and does not take into account numerous other aspects of life demonstrates the complete impossibility of abiogenesis.

One can infer by deduction that since abiogenesis is impossible, the only explanation for life is another life source, which inevitably leads to the presence of a divine creator. Furthermore, intangible elements of the human experience allude to this being more than possible. For example, if a group of people were to be asked to imagine a random image, does one have any way to quantify the image? Sure one can measure brain wave activity, but one does not have any way of knowing without being told the exact colors, dimensions, and specific details of this image. While someone could state what they are, there is no way to measure the truthfulness of

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the statement. However, while intangible and immeasurable, one would agree that such things exist due to common experience.

Can the atheist say then that it is impossible that a spiritual force, which transcends our ability to perceive and measure exists and acts intentionally and deliberately? Can the atheist say with 100% certainty that we as Christians have not perceived the presence of an omnipotent force that functions intelligently although they have not?

In addition to the aforementioned factual elements, God's existence is suggested overwhelmingly by the supernatural miracles, which occur today. On December 7, 2007, Alcides Moreno fell 47 stories when his contraption gave way while he was washing the building's windows (Barron, 2008). Moreno survived this fall and was able to walk again a year later. His survival and regaining of the ability to walk was referred to as a miracle, which is a term rarely used in scientific literature. By definition, a miracle is a favorable outcome that contradicts scientific law and can only be explained by divine intervention (Oxford Languages, 2021).

This event is considered miraculous because with respect to a freefall 3,000 Newtons of pressure on the human body exerts a force that causes death on impact (The Physics of Death, 2021). The researcher has experienced some making the argument that the 1,250 pound platform Moreno laid down on and held onto, provides

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a possible explanation for his survival. However, the force of the fall given a weight of 100 pounds, which is less than his actual weight, and the weight of the 1250 pound platform, would be calculated at greater than 8,000,000 Newtons of pressure. Even assuming that the platform COULD absorb 99.9% of the pressure, the pressure absorbed by Moreno's body would still equal at a minimum 8,000 Newtons, almost 2.7 times the amount of pressure that kills on impact. This by the laws of physics CANNOT happen, yet it did. Hence, the scientific argument that everything has a cause applies here. Can the atheist swear that the cause wasn't an intangible force that acts deliberately and intelligently whose presence cannot be measured?

In alluding to the truth of God's presence, the aforementioned facts could stand alone. However, more proof is evident via qualitative evidence in the experiences reported by former atheists who have come to believe in God's existence. One such case is the case of Mr. Robert Melnichuk, a former atheist, who upon examining the Bible became intrigued by the fact that there were elements of eyewitness testimony that he saw daily in his career as a homicide investigator. Using his investigational skills, he was able to determine that the events of the Bible were fact and not as he termed it initially "moralistic mythology. (Atheism: Why I Converted to Christianity, 2013)" Melnichuk further concluded that there were properties of

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the Gospels, which very closely resembled the eyewitness accounts of an event witnessed by multiple individuals, which gives more credence to their accuracy. As Mr. Melnichuk examined more closely the properties of the gospels, he launched an all out investigation using both history and the gospels and that was ultimately how he came to faith. Based on his testimony, the theme that becomes evident is that there is more to the human experience than science and reason alone can describe. By applying known investigative techniques to the scriptures, he discovered that what appeared to be mythology at first glance was actually provable and true in terms of the tangible and intangible.

Another example is the case of Mrs. Jennifer Fulweiler, who reported being born into an atheist family and not even believing in God as a child. Throughout her life, she describes her experience as a diet of reason and belief in what was provable and observable. (Atheist to Christian Testimony, 2014) When she began studying the scriptures and other world religions, she was not completely persuaded, and decided to put out every hard question on a blog. As stated by Fulweiler (2014) "Christians and atheists had the scientific concepts correct, yet the Christian responses more accurately portrayed the human experience." As a result, she became compelled to believe in the truth of the scriptures although they were

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counterintuitive to her. In this case the theme once more is that science explains very well the way the world works.

However, there is more than simply the tangible with respect to the human experience. In fact, it was the intangible elements that made the most compelling case.

In adding up the evidence in its totality, it makes a most compelling case for God's existence as a true and real presence. Primarily, through logic alone, one may rightly deduce that the cause of life was living and not inanimate by the disproof of spontaneous and abiogenesis respectively. Moreover, contrary to the popular contentions of some in the atheist community, there are elements of human existence that are intangible and immeasurable, yet are very real. Therefore, the atheist cannot rightly say that it is impossible that an intelligent force, imperceptible to the human mind and senses, was behind a miraculous event that contradicts science so perfectly as to baffle even the most intelligent professionals. Furthermore, qualitative evidence, which is held valid in the scientific community as evidence based on factors that are impossible to measure, has seen recurrence of the same theme; reason, ration, and science alone are not enough to explain the human experience. Thus, two former atheists, through unbiased investigation concluded rightly that there was another side to the human experience that was not quantitative, but qualitative.

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While acknowledging the tangible, it was a combination of that AND the intangible, which more FULLY captured the human experience and proved God's existence through inference.

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